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Lorca's research in Web of Science and Scopus from a bibliometric gender perspective

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Abstract

Federico García Lorca (FGL) was a prominent poet and playwright in 20th-century Spanish literature. García Lorca, known for his defense of the role of women in a society that historically marginalized them, built strong female characters and critics of traditional roles. This study examines the relationship between gender and the selection of research topics on Federico García Lorca, an area that remains underexplored. To fill this gap, we analyze the keywords used by authors in publications indexed in two major bibliographic databases: Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. We construct cognitive maps that identify six key research areas within the scientific literature related to FGL. We then present a comparative analysis that examines how studies of Lorca's work have developed from a gender perspective. This approach highlights the increasing contributions of female scholars in a traditionally male-dominated field. We hope that this study will contribute to expanding the literature on how to analyze the influence of gender in the selection of research topics and the type of knowledge generated.

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1. Introduction

Federico García Lorca's advocacy for freedom, gender equality, and the defense of marginalized groups based on ideology, sexual orientation, or race, has made him a cornerstone for the LGBTQ+ community, the ethnic minorities (e.g. Roma community), and gender equality advocates. His politicized figure, alongside the cultural and historical value of his work, continues to inspire a wide range of academic inquiry.

The co-word analysis method (Callon et al. 1991) is considered one of the most effective tools for mapping and decoding the cognitive structure of a scientific field (Leydesdorff 2007; Leydesdorff & Nerges 2017). Beyond revealing the underlying framework of a discipline, it also identifies and evaluates its key research areas (Vargas-Quesada et al. 2017). Its greatest strength lies in its ability to detect emerging trends across fields, capturing their development through dynamic, evolutionary mapping (Vargas-Quesada et al. 2023). The resulting "science maps" not only validate but also highlight the multidisciplinary impact of studies on Lorca. Beyond the academic community, these visualizations serve as strategic tools for science policymakers, enabling a clearer understanding of the complex interconnections within the research landscape and supporting data-driven decision-making in research management (Muñoz-Écija et al. 2022).

This study introduces a novel approach to analyzing research on García Lorca, focusing on gendered topic selection in academic discourse. Through mapping techniques, it visualizes the contributions of female researchers by examining data from two leading academic databases, Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus (Moya-Anegón et al. 2007; Chadegani et al. 2013). By analyzing keywords, this research identifies key thematic areas and their evolution over time, offering a comprehensive overview of scholarly trends in Lorca studies, distinguishing by gender.

One of the standout features of this study is its comparative gender analysis, providing a unique perspective on how both women and men have shaped this field. By using maps to display connections between key topics, this study charts the landscape of Lorca's research, highlighting literary advances and the impact of

gender dynamics. It also emphasizes women's contributions in a male-dominated field, encouraging reflection on their role in shaping knowledge of Lorca's legacy.

In recent years, research on the gender gap in academia has increased through bibliometric methods and approaches. González-Salmón et al. (2024a) investigate the experiences of men and women in science from different methodological perspectives, focusing on gender disambiguation techniques, units of analysis, and causality issues. They identify the main research topics and classify them into three groups based on differences within academia, the causes of these differences, and their main consequences. Using ARIMA and exponential smoothing prediction models, and analyzing influencing factors using Bayesian networks, they attempt to predict when each country will reach gender parity and what factors might influence the increase in the proportion of women in science (González-Salmón et al. 2024b). The gender disparity in scientific research is significantly influenced by country of origin and discipline. Fields such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), economics and philosophy tend to have larger gender gaps (Aramayona et al. 2022; Charlesworth and Banaji 2019), with disparities being more pronounced compared to the humanities and some social sciences, where parity is more frequently achieved (Demaine 2021).

2. Background

Over the years, various studies have examined authors' impact or the level of interdisciplinarity providing new insights into knowledge and research trends within specific disciplines. White and McCain (2000) pioneered such studies by introducing CAMEOs as a method for representing and analyzing an author's role within their scholarly ecosystem. Later, White (2002) expanded on this concept by developing author-centered maps, using Derek John de Solla Price as a case study and further refining CAMEOs as tools for data collection. Building on this approach, Trillo-Domínguez and De-Moya-Anegón (2007) mapped Marshall McLuhan's intellectual influences and the impact of his work, while Lucas and Vargas-Quesada (2015) examined Pierre Bourdieu's influence in Information Science. Similarly, Chen (2018) honored Eugene Garfield by highlighting his legacy in scientometrics, and Restrepo (2018) conducted a bibliometric study on Hope A. Olson, exploring the application of feminist theories in knowledge organization. More recently, Do Carmo et al. (2023) analyzed Jürgen Habermas's

scientific output, while Felizardo et al. (2023) examined the academic impact of Elinor Ostrom. Finally, Vargas Quesada et al. (2023) honored Loet Leydesdorff by using overlapping maps to analyze his scientific trajectory from five different perspectives. These studies underscore the importance of bibliometric techniques to uncover the structure of academic inquiry and offer a more critical and nuanced perspective on the representation of different groups within the scientific community. Besides, these studies inspired us to focus on the gender perspective to study elections on topics (Kozłowski et al. 2022).

Regarding gender studies, according to Fernández-Alonso and Barros-Del Río (pp. 18, 2021), between the 1920s and 1930s, Langston Hughes, attracted by García Lorca's poetry, wrote several poems that attest to his interest in the Gypsy tradition, where he must have perceived the traces of Africanism. Hughes was the first author to write about Lorca's gender perspective from a generic point of view. Later, numerous articles would be published on the role of women in Lorca's different works. In his poetry collection, Lorca champions women's equality, although it is in his plays where he has a more methodical impact. It should be noted that, of the 12 plays written by García Lorca, women are the protagonists in eight of them, in three they play a prominent role, and only one, "The public", is more focused on homosexuality and women play a secondary role. The three rural dramas (Blood wedding, Yerma and The house of Bernarda Alba) together with Doña Rosita the spinster and The prodigious shoemaker, have been the inspiration for numerous scientific articles that analyze matriarchy, the alienation of women, abuse, etc.

3. Objectives

Based on the above, this article sets out to pursue two main objectives: a) to represent and study the cognitive structure of research on García Lorca in general, and from a gender perspective, and b) to explore the historical evolution of research on García Lorca from a gender perspective.

4. Methodology

The databases used in this research are Scopus and Web of Science. "Scopus is characterized by its broad multidisciplinary coverage, especially in social sciences, arts, and humanities, [...] and WoS by its robust and reliable publication metadata,

as well as its impact metrics, which provide crucial information for assessing academic trends and the influence of research” (Saoualih et al. 2024).

The data was retrieved on May 18, 2024, using the following queries: WoS Core Collection: Topic = (“garcia-lorca”) –745 records. Scopus: TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH (“garcia lorca”) – 379 records. No restrictions were placed on document type or language, allowing for a comprehensive dataset. We focused on records from 1946 up to 2023, the most recent complete year, initially retrieving 1,124 entries. After merging data and removing duplicates, the final dataset comprised 891 works, representing García Lorca's research from 1946 to 2023 in both databases.

The use of algorithms to determine the gender of authors was ruled out since journals do not incorporate this information into their metadata in self-reported information (Ribarovska et al. 2021), and the use of automated processes in bibliometric studies involves several significant challenges. First, names do not always reliably indicate gender, as many are unisex or culturally specific, which can lead to misclassification (González-Salmón & Robinson-García 2024). Second, algorithms typically perform better with Western or Anglo-Saxon names and are less accurate with Asian or non-Latin names, which can introduce bias and reduce accuracy (Karimi et al. 2016). Third, many algorithms assume a binary gender model, ignoring non-binary, transgender, or other gender identities, thereby rendering diverse gender expressions invisible (Lindqvist et al. 2021; Rasmussen et al. 2019). Furthermore, inferring gender from names can raise privacy concerns and may not reflect people's self-identified gender (Ribarovska et al. 2021).

To analyze the temporal evolution of research production by gender, we identify four distinct periods: 1946-2008 “*Early Advances*”; 2009-2014 “*Expansion*”; 2015-2019; “*Equilibrium*” and 2020-2023 “*Consolidation*” (Fig.1). Additionally, we use the Total Link Strength of each node to assess its prominence within each period.

Fig. 1. Temporal evolution of publications with the four delimited periods.

Keywords served as the primary unit of analysis to uncover the cognitive structure of García Lorca's research, with their co-occurrence serving as the foundation for our analysis, revealing thematic relationships and research clusters. Using VOSviewer (Van Eck et al. 2010) we construct cognitive maps, where nodes represent keywords, with their size indicating frequency in the dataset; links represent connections, showing relationships between themes (the closer the nodes, the stronger the connection). Clusters, marked in different colors, highlight distinct research areas (Waltman et al. 2010). This visual approach allows us to track the evolution of research themes over time. For the development of this study, a thesaurus was created and is available at: [10.5281/zenodo.14811279](https://zenodo.org/record/14811279).

The cognitive structure or base map was created by mapping the keywords from the 891 retrieved documents across both databases, categorized into the previously defined research periods. Two overlays of visual elements were then incorporated into the map to differentiate the authors' gender (Fig. 2). To ensure a more precise analysis, 70 publications corresponding to literal translations of poems by García Lorca were eliminated, the same was done with articles co-authored by both genders were excluded, representing 2.7% of the total. Additionally, 0.85% of the articles could not be identified in terms of gender, and the same percentage corresponds to editorials unsigned. Regarding male authorship, 455 articles were signed by 350 authors (58%). Meanwhile, 280 female researchers authored a total of 329 articles (42%).

5. Results

5.1. The evolution in the number of publications according to genres

The historical journey from 1946 to 2023 reveals a clear process: from invisibility to consolidation. Women have gone from being absent figures in research on Lorca to becoming key protagonists in the critical development surrounding his work.

In the "Early Advances" period, from 1946 to 2008, women authors began to occupy a marginal but growing position. In the "Expansion" period, from 2009 to 2014, they emerged strongly and began to take the lead. From 2015 to 2019, in the "Equilibrium" period, they achieved full stability. Finally, in the "Consolidation" period, from 2020 to 2023, their role became normalized as essential and unavoidable.

This evolution is not only numerical but deeply symbolic: it reflects the transformation of the academic and cultural space, opening the way to new perspectives, perspectives, and ways of understanding the work of one of the most emblematic authors of Hispanic literature.

5.1.1. *Early Advances (1946–2008)*

For more than six decades, the authorship landscape in studies on Federico García Lorca was dominated by men. Between 1946 and 2008, male researchers authored 205 publications, compared to 77 by women, representing just 27% of the total.

Until the mid-1970s, female participation was virtually nonexistent, and it was only in 1976 that the first female contributions began to appear. Throughout the 1980s and 1990s, this participation increased slowly but progressively, becoming consolidated in the 2000s. The year 2008 marked a milestone: women published 15 works, surpassing men for the first time, who authored 11. This figure symbolizes the close of a long period in which female participation moved from marginality to an active, albeit still secondary, role in global terms. During this period, women gradually joined the Lorca academic field, moving from invisibility to becoming a relevant and rising presence.

5.1.2. Expansion (2009–2014)

Between 2009 and 2014, a decisive shift occurred: women equaled and even surpassed men in the number of publications. In these six years, women published 58 publications compared to 53 for men, reaching a female proportion of 52.3%. This period represents a true turning point. In years such as 2011 (16 publications by women compared to 10 by men) and 2014 (22 each), a real balance in research production is observed, with growing acceptance and legitimization of the female voice in studies on Lorca.

The "Expansion" period is marked by the definitive emergence of women as protagonists of critical analysis of Lorca, consolidating their presence not only in quantity but also in influence and analytical depth.

5.1.3. Equilibrium (2015–2019)

The 2015–2019 five-year period is characterized by stability in female participation, which is no longer temporary but structural. Women published 82 works during this period, compared to 97 by men, representing 45.8% of the total. This balance is evident year after year, with figures that barely vary. 2018 is particularly noteworthy, when women published 17 studies compared to 16 by men, a clear sign of effective parity.

In the "Equilibrium" period, gender equality in authorship is not an exception, but the norm. Women have achieved a solid presence, becoming key figures within the Lorca academic canon.

5.1.4. Consolidation (2020–2023)

In the last four years, the trend toward equality has continued, albeit with a slight increase in male authorship. Between 2020 and 2023, men authored 79 publications and women 60, the latter remaining at a stable 43% of the total.

Despite not outnumbering men, female authors maintain a constant and robust presence, with a minimum of 13 publications per year. In 2023, for example, women authored 15 works, compared to 22 for men.

This latest phase shows that female participation no longer requires validation: it is an integral and recognized part of the academic discourse on García Lorca, with continuity, prestige, and solid research.

5.2. Structure cognitive of studies on García Lorca

Figure 2 shows the global cognitive structure of studies on García Lorca (2a), along with their overlays corresponding to each gender (2b for males y 2c for females). Therefore, six research fronts on Lorca were identified (cognitive structure).

(Fig. 2.a.) Cognitive structure: <https://tinyurl.com/34z5xdyt>

(Fig. 2.b.) Male overlay: <https://tinyurl.com/47h42hjx>

(Fig. 2.c.) Female overlay: <https://tinyurl.com/mu873svt>

Fig. 2. (a,b and c). Global research on Lorca's oeuvre and research by gender.

In Front 1, “Literature, identity, and reception” (red), in both sexes, many keywords in this category are linked to literature and the performing arts, theater, poetry, playwriting, and stage performances. They are also grouped around identity and culture, including terms such as: gender, sexuality, andalusian folk music, flamenco, and hispanic literature. There are also numerous references to reception and translation with terms linked to the criticism, reception, translation, and circulation of her work in different cultural and historical contexts.

In Front 2, “Avant-garde, interculturality, and memory” (green), studies focus on representing the artistic, disruptive, and aesthetic dimensions of the works of this historical period, and of García Lorca in particular, encompassed within the different avant-garde movements and their aesthetics. Represented with terms such as avant-garde, cubism, surrealism, poetic irrationalism, imagism, radical aesthetics, performance aesthetics, formal analysis, aesthetics of 27, expressionism, and modernism. “Interculturality” reflects the intersection of cultures, languages, and traditions that influence and surround Lorca's work, and its study includes terms such as andalusian arabic poetry, bilingualism, italian reception, hispanism in the US, translation studies, transnationalism, spanish/chinese, internationalism, intercultural class, cosmopolitanism, and comparative literature. Finally, ‘memory’

highlights the historical, political and testimonial content of many articles, especially those related to the Civil War, francoism and historical memory with words such as francoism, democratic transition, republican exile, World War II, trauma, memorial culture, civil authority, fascism, exhumations and early twentieth-century.

In Front 3, “Philosophy, aesthetics, and cinema” (blue), an existential, psychoanalytic and philosophical reading of the works is indicated, focused on desire, death, the repressed and the unconscious with terms such as death drive, unconscious, depth psychology, narcissism, sadomasochism, eroticism, fear, thanatos, CG Jung, Sigmund Freud, Sabina Spielrein, Heinz Kohut, Nietzsche, Husserl, Marc Richir. “Aesthetics” covers both artistic creation and reflection on the languages of expression, from poetry to cinema and theater with a look at the involvement of some authors and the aesthetics of the avant-garde movements to which they belonged. Words like aesthetics, aesthetics surrealism, architecture, mise-en-abyme, metatheater, literary city, theory of the duende (teoría del duende), ode to Salvador Dalí, prose poems, greguería, metaphysics of art, Max Aub, modernism, postmodernism. In this front, keywords like auteur cinema, cinematic shamanism, contemplative cinema, Luis Buñuel, Buster Keaton, Ingmar Bergman, Francis Ford Coppola, Martin Scorsese, movies, spanish silent film, anamorphosis, hallucination, space, etc., are also grouped and connected, which define a critical attention to cinema as an expressive medium, including both cinematographic influences on García Lorca and its visual appropriation and adaptations.

In Front 4, “Theater, identity and values” (yellow), the terms clearly connect around stage representation, intermedial adaptations, and cultural identity, all in dialogue with religious, philosophical, and political thought. The stage and dramaturgical dimension of Lorca's works and their contemporary reinterpretation in various formats is reflected in the use of keywords such as theatre practice, mise-en-scène, drama, performance, stage sculpture, puppet theater, sacramental play, theatricality, literary script, adaptation, film adaptation, national theatre, twentieth-century spanish drama, retablillo de Don Cristóbal, Amor don Perlimplín, Doña Rosita la soltera, Don Cristóbal y la Señá Rosita, La vida es sueño, Calderón de la Barca, Shakespeare, etc. Another grouping of words focuses on how the plays and their adaptations address identity, otherness, and social and cultural tensions. As is the case with words like diaspora, Roma community, jewishness, anti-semitism,

regional identity, national identity, heteronormativity, manhood crisis, identity construction, cultural assimilation, andalucian television, caribbean, spanish dance, spanish cinema, black performance. The mention of ‘values’ is due to the interest shown in the religious and philosophical values present in Lorca's works or in their rereadings, with special attention to symbolism and the ethics of meaning, which are embodied in words like christianity, eucharist, sacrifice, transubstantiation, auto sacramental, roman catholicism, enlightenment, hermeneutics, translation ethics, dialectic, Ortega y Gasset, and Goethe's Faust.

In front 5, “Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks” (violet), shows how García Lorca's poetry reflects a productive tension between poetic innovation and continuity with historical models, with special attention to poetic forms, images, and styles. It includes terms such as modern poetry, literary tradition, pastoral elegy, dramatic monologue, canon, Garcilaso, Rimbaud, Walt Whitman, Arthur Rimbaud, Stefan George, Jack Spicer, Nicanor Parra, Bob Dylan, objective correlative, metaphorical engine, and verbal imagination. In this regard, he also focuses on political activism and historical and cultural memory, especially in relation to revolutionary contexts, exile, and cultural resistance. This is reflected in keywords such as Spanish Civil War, anti-fascism, nueva canción chilena, songs of the Spanish Civil War (canciones de la Guerra Civil española), emergency theater, Chile, Soviet Union, Cyprus, Rolando Alarcón, Diego Rivera, Miklós Radnóti, Manuel Altolaguirre, and Winnipeg. And in another order of knowledge, there is a grouping of terms such as reception, translational norms, literary gatekeeper, authorial image, unpublished works, philosophical body, Paris, Latin America, Russia, Sweden, Cyprus, Poulenc, Geoffrey Parsons, Vera Kuteyshikova, Lorca play-writing, queer studies, and female authors, which explore the international circulation of Lorca's work and its reinterpretation from diverse cultures, genres and languages, both from the perspective of criticism and artistic creation.

Front 6, “Metadata and social networks” (light blue), this front summarizes the keywords of an article that is very different from the others: it consists of the study of networks applied to the relationship of female characters in the plays *Yerma* and *Doña Rosita, la soltera*, through this method, it aims to highlight quantitative data resulting from the analysis of elements such as degree centrality and the measurement of the centrality of eigenvectors.

5.3. Fronts and keywords associated with gender, equality, and sexuality studies

In the previous section, we saw how the knowledge map groups keywords into six different knowledge clusters; however, not all terms referring to gender, equality, or sexuality appear in the same grouping. This is because the interdisciplinary nature of some studies or their specificity means that certain words in this grouping are distributed across several groups. Let's see how this distribution occurs below.

- (1) Front 1: “Literature, identity, and reception”. This front includes the majority of terms directly linked to issues of gender identity, feminism, and sexuality.
 - Censorship and homosexuality, eminent-maricones, gender, gender studies, homoerotic verse, homophobia, homosexual love, irish feminism, irish woman, La casa de Bernada Alba, la novia, lgbtq+, marginality, matriarchy, motherhood, otherness, queer subject, sexuality, travestied quotations, women spaces, women repression, Yerma.
- (2) Front 2: “Avant-garde, interculturality and memory”. This front is the most directly related to the intersectional study of gender, identity, and global representations of dissent.
 - feminine agency, femininity, fertility, gender representations
- (3) Front 3: “Philosophy, aesthetics, and cinema”. This front is the one that provides a theoretical and aesthetic approach to queer studies and representations of the body and sexuality.
 - Heterosexuality, Homosexuality, queer modernism, queer theory
- (4) Front 4: “Theatre, identity and values”. On this front, religious values are addressed, only heterosexuality is treated as an acceptable sexual orientation.
 - Heteronormativity

(5) Front 5: “Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks”. These keywords refer to performative practices that intersect with queer studies, performance theory, and dissident gender representations.

- Female authors, queer studies, duality and homoeroticism

(6) Front 6: “Metadata and social networks”. This section exclusively examines an article that specifically studies the relevance of female characters in the plots of two plays.

- Female main characters

5.4. Keyword variation and relevance in female authors

Figure 3 (a, b, c, and d) shows the trends in research on García Lorca from a female perspective, as well as the evolution of its key terms over time, ordered by their ‘score’: weight <Total Link Strength> (Table 1).

Fig. 3. (a, b, c and d). Maps of male research on Lorca’s oeuvre by period

(**Fig. 3.a.**) 1948-2008 ‘First advances’: <https://tinyurl.com/73u46aj7>

(**Fig. 3. b.**) 2009-2014 ‘Expansion’: <https://tinyurl.com/y8k2f773>

(**Fig. 3. c.**) 2015-2019 ‘Equilibrium’: <https://tinyurl.com/4rcr7kbv>

(**Fig. 3. D.**) 2020-2023 ‘Consolidation’: <https://tinyurl.com/25xzy6e7>

1946-2008 'First advances'		2009-2014 'Period of expansion'		2015-2019 'Period of equilibrium'		2020-2023: 'Period of consolidation'	
Label	Score	Label	Score	Label	Score	Label	Score
garcia lorca	96	garcia lorca	126	garcia lorca	162	garcia lorca	100
movies	32	salvador dali	19	translation studies	29	poetry	28
poetry	24	city	18	flamenco	28	theater	22
auteur cinema	23	poetry	18	romancero gitano	27	poeta en nyc	16
cg jung	23	death	17	manuel de falla	25	feminism	15
cinema of redemption	23	luis bunuel	15	avant garde	22	20th century spanish literature	14
cinematic shamanism	23	myth	15	andalusian folk music	19	intertextuality	14
contemplative cinema	23	sigmund freud	14	cante jondo	19	spanish poetry	14
david putnam	23	intertextuality	13	demofilo	19	neopopulism	13
depth psychology	23	contemporary spanish	12	moor/morisco	19	fray luis de leon	12

Table 1. Women's keywords with the highest score, weight by period.

During 1946-2008 “First advances”, female production was nearly nonexistent until 1976, followed by a gradual increase in the 1990s and 2000s, though it never reached male production levels. Interest emerged in Lorca’s connection to cinema (auteur cinema, Coppola) and deep psychology (Freud, Jung), reflecting a focus on film adaptation and psychoanalysis.

In 2009-2014 “Expansion”, female participation grew, surpassing male production in 2014 (22 vs. 18 articles). Studies on the Generation of 27, Dalí, and Buñuel gained prominence, emphasizing intertextuality. Additionally, themes such as motherhood and mythology emerged, suggesting an increasing focus on femininity within Lorca's literary work.

During 2015-2019 “Equilibrium”, female production remained close to male output (20 vs. 19 in 2019). Research explored Lorca’s relationship with Andalusian popular music (flamenco, cante jondo) and avant-garde movements (surrealism, avant-garde).

Lastly, we meet the period 2020-2023 “Consolidation”. In the most recent period, female production stabilizes, though it does not consistently surpass the production rates of their male counterparts. Research increasingly focuses on poetry and theater, with an emphasis on mysticism (San Juan de la Cruz, Hallaj), and contemporary issues like feminism and neopopulism.

5.5. Keyword variation and relevance in male authors

Fig. 4. (a, b, c, y d) shows the trends in research on García Lorca from a male perspective, as well as the evolution of its key terms over time (Table 2).

Fig. 4. (a, b, c and d). Maps of male research on Lorca’s oeuvre by period.

(**Fig. 4. a.**) 1948-2008 ‘First advances’: <https://tinyurl.com/ftvwstrz>

(**Fig. 4. b.**) 2009-2014 ‘Expansion’: <https://tinyurl.com/3n4m2cjj>

(**Fig. 4 c.**) 2015-2019 ‘Equilibrium’: <https://tinyurl.com/7javcnp2>

(**Fig. 4. d.**) 2020-2023 ‘Consolidation’ <https://tinyurl.com/426r2zyx>

1946-2008 First advances'		2009-2014 'Period of expansion'		2015-2019 Period of equilibrium'		2020-2023: 'Period of consolidation'	
Label	Score	Label	Score	Label	Score	Label	Score
garcia lorca	52	garcia lorca	163	garcia lorca	152	garcia lorca	179
myth	11	spain	32	spanish civil war	30	poeta en nyc	37
criticism	6	spanish civil war	27	teoria del duende	25	surrealism	30
dialectic	6	translation studies	18	homosexuality	20	poetry	23
economics	6	blood wedding	16	lorca play-writing	20	time	20
father	6	modernism	16	manuel altolaguirre	20	painting	19
fragmentation	6	poetry	16	soviet union	20	rafael alberti	18
gaston baquero	6	censorship	15	unpublished works	20	translation studies	17
luis cernuda	6	amor don perlimplin	14	poetry	18	death	15
pablo neruda	6	theater	14	russia	18	drawings	14

Table 2. Men keywords with the highest score, weight by period.

During the “First advances” period (1946-2008), the keywords reflect an initial focus on the mythification of Lorca and his relationship with other poets such as Neruda and Cernuda, along with themes of criticism, dialectics, and poetic realism. In “Period of expansion” (2009-2014), the analysis diversifies,

incorporating studies on the Spanish Civil War, censorship, theatre, and translation, showing an interest in their historical and literary context. During the “Period of equilibrium” (2015-2019), themes such as homosexuality, exile, and gender emerge, indicating a turn towards more socio-political and theoretical approaches. Finally, in the “Period of Consolidation” (2020-2023), a deepening of the field of surrealism, poetry, and visual arts is observed, linking Lorca with broader aesthetic and philosophical expressions.

6. Discussion

Does the increase in female participation in García Lorca studies reflect what has happened in other disciplines? As we saw in the introduction to this paper, gender disparity in scientific research is significantly influenced by country of origin and discipline (Aramayona et al. 2022; Charlesworth and Banaji 2019), with parity most frequently achieved in the social sciences (Demaine 2021).

Although women's participation in academia has increased in various areas, this increase has not been uniform across all stages of women's professional careers, as it is directly linked to gender representation in high-level positions in terms of productivity (number of articles), research impact (number of citations), and co-authorship networks (degree of connectivity) (Jaramillo et al. 2025). Their study, which analyses more than 80 million articles published from 1975 to 2020 in 19 academic fields, reveals that women continue to be a minority in all areas, with physics, geology and mathematics having the lowest percentage of articles written by women (14%), followed by psychology, with the highest percentage (39%), with the female proportion in social sciences and humanities reaching 35.85%, reflecting greater inclusion and parity in these areas of knowledge.

[...] in most fields, women and men with comparable productivity levels and professional age tend to achieve different levels of citations, with women tending to benefit more from co-authorships, while men tend to benefit more from productivity, especially in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics. (Jaramillo, et al. pp. 1, 2025)

The evolution of female authorship in studies on Federico García Lorca shows a positive trend toward parity, especially notable in the Expansion and

Equilibrium periods. Although almost complete parity was reached in 2014, in subsequent years the female proportion stabilized at around 43–45%.

Without a doubt, García Lorca's oft-mentioned preference for positioning women as the central focus of his work and his continued call for gender equality can be considered a motivation for women to adopt García Lorca as a primary focus of their research. However, one cannot ignore the fact that a large number of male authors, imbued with García Lorca's philosophy, conduct studies on this subject.

The comparative study of the themes addressed by the male authors in each stage reveals a significant interest in historical themes, political history, and censorship. Incipient gender studies are marginally addressed, and analyses of specific theatrical works are carried out, offering more dispersed approaches, lacking a clear focus, and centred on external concepts applied to his work. The women focused more on Lorca as a direct object of study and as a mythical figure within cinema and symbolic psychology; they delve more deeply into the author's artistic and psychological context, maintaining a focus more centred on Lorca himself, as evidenced by the similarity in the size of the sphere corresponding to García Lorca in the maps for both genders and the numerical proximity between the García Lorca scores for men and women in the tables, despite the fact that the latter have a smaller proportion of articles.

7. Final remarks

Our study shows different interests in “Lorca’s oeuvre” from a gender perspective. Research on Lorca has evolved differently depending on the gender of the scholars. Male researchers have shifted from traditional perspectives focusing on his mythification, the Spanish Civil War, and critical reception to a more recent emphasis on aesthetics, surrealism, and visual arts. In contrast, female scholars have explored intertextuality, cinema, psychoanalysis, and the representation of femininity in his work, while also investigating his influence on other art forms, music, and mysticism. Furthermore, female-led research increasingly addresses themes like feminism and transculturation, reflecting a more critical, contemporary approach. These findings show that female scholars tend to examine the circulation, transformation, and translation of Lorca’s work, with a focus on its social and gender implications, while male researchers concentrate more on historical,

aesthetic, and literary analysis. This distinction highlights the differing thematic priorities and gendered perspectives that shape Lorca's studies.

We hope this approach sheds light on the relationship between a researcher's gender and the type of knowledge they generate, offering insights into how gender may influence the selection of research topics.

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